

The Dark Sides of Modern Science: Credit Attribution, Citation and Impact

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Abstract: This is the sixth article in our series “The Dark Sides of Modern Science” and is about the credit attribution, citation and impact in the scientific circles and literature (where science means knowledge in general). The remarks that we stated in the Introduction of the first article of this series (i.e. “Knowledge Production and Authoring”) generally apply to this article and hence we do not need to repeat.

Keywords: Ethics of science, ethics of knowledge, morality in science, academic misconduct, corruption in science, corruption related to science.

Contents

Abstract	1
Table of Contents	2
1 Citation Metrics	3
2 Citation Misconduct	8
3 Citation Biases and Disparities	13
4 Questionable Types and Practices of Citation	17
5 Citation Value	21
6 Citation and Artificial Intelligence	24
7 Citation and Questionable Publishing	25
8 Citation and Retraction	27
9 Citation and Indexing Engines and Databases	30
10 Awards and Honors	34
11 Idolization, Fabrication and Inflation	36
12 Celebrity Culture	39
13 ORCID	40
14 Grade Inflation	40
15 Evaluating and Quantifying Credit	42
16 Fake Qualifications	43
17 Miscellaneous	43

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5 Citation Value

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63. [What the Nobel Prizes Are Not.](#)
64. [The Nobel Prize Is Bad And We Should Feel Bad.](#)
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11 Idolization, Fabrication and Inflation

Also see some of the previous articles in this series related to things like plagiarism and fraud of scientists (especially the famous ones); e.g. “Plagiarism” section in the first article and “Fraud, Fabrication, Cheating and Dishonesty” section in the fourth article.

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